

A DETAILED REVIEW ON ANTIFUNGAL AGENT

**Wasim J. Bagwan^{1*}, Ravi U. Kurhade², Neha B. Bayas³, Shivani S. Chelkar³,
Shabana A. Patel³, Nikita D. Kamble³**

¹Assistant Professor Department of Pharmacy, MDA School Of Pharmacy Kolpa Latur, MH, India, 413512.

²Principal Department of Pharmacy, MDA School of Pharmacy Kolpa Latur, MH, India, 413512.

³Student Department of Pharmacy, MDA School of Pharmacy Kolpa Latur, MH, India, 413512.

Article Received on 15 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 06 March 2026,
Article Published on 10 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18936081>

***Corresponding Author**

Wasim J. Bagwan

Assistant Professor Department of
Pharmacy, MDA School of
Pharmacy Kolpa Latur, MH, India,
413512.

How To Cite This Article: Wasim J. Bagwan^{1*}, Ravi U. Kurhade², Neha B. Bayas³, Shivani S. Chelkar³, Shabana A. Patel³, Nikita D. Kamble³. (2026). A Detailed Review On Antifungal Agent. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(3), 1323–1336. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Invasive fungal infections are becoming an increasingly important cause of human mortality and morbidity, particularly for immunocompromised populations. The fungal pathogens *Candida albicans*, *Coccidioides immitis*, and *Aspergillus fumigatus* collectively contribute to over 1 million human deaths annually. Hence, the importance of safe and effective antifungal therapeutics for the practice of modern medicine has never been greater. Given that fungi are eukaryote like their human host, the number of unique molecular targets that can be exploited for drug development remains limited. Only three classes of molecules are currently approved for the treatment of invasive mycosis. The efficacy of these agents is compromised by host toxicity, fungistatic activity, or the emergence of drug resistance in pathogen populations. Here we describe our current arsenal of antifungal and highlight current strategies that are being employed to improve the therapeutic safety and

efficacy of these drugs. We discuss state-of-the-art approaches to discover novel chemical matter with antifungal activity and highlight some of the most promising new targets for antifungal drug development. We feature the benefits of combination therapy as a strategy to

expand our current repertoire of antifungal and discuss the antifungal combinations that have shown the greatest potential for clinical development.

KEYWORDS: Antifungal agent, Amphotericin B; flucytosine; triazol;echinocandis; invasive fungal infection; resistance sidarphores.

INTRODUCTION

An antifungal agent is a drug that selectively eliminates fungal pathogens from a host with minimal toxicity to the host. The development of antifungal agents has lagged behind that of antibacterial agents. This is a predictable consequence of the cellular structure of the organisms involved. Bacteria are prokaryotic and hence offer numerous structural and metabolic targets that differ from those of the human host. Fungi, in contrast, are eukaryotes, and consequently most agents toxic to fungi are also toxic to the host.

Furthermore, because fungi generally grow slowly and often in multicellular forms, they are more difficult to quantify than bacteria. This difficulty complicates experiments designed to evaluate the *in vitro* or *in vivo* properties of a potential antifungal agent. Despite these limitations, numerous advances have been made in developing new antifungal agents and in understanding the existing ones. This chapter summarizes the more common antifungal agents. Three groups of drugs are emphasized: the polyenes, the azoles, and one antimetabolite. Table 76-1 summarizes the most important antifungal agents and their most common uses. An antifungal medication, also known as an antimycotic medication, is a pharmaceutical fungicide or fungistatic used to treat and prevent mycosis such as athlete's foot, ringworm, candidiasis, serious systemic infections such as cryptococcal meningitis, and others. Steadily with the rise and fall of AIDS-related mycoses, And the change in spectrum of fatal disseminated fungal Infections that has accompanied changes in therapeutic Immunosuppressive therapies. The search for new Molecular targets for antifungals has generated con- Severable research using modern genomic approaches, So far without generating new agents for clinical use. Meanwhile, six new antifungal agents have just Reached, or are approaching, the clinic. Three are new Triazoles, with extremely broad antifungal spectra, and three are echinocandins, which inhibit synthesis of fun-Gal cell wall polysaccharides – a new mode of action. In Addition, the sordarins represent a novel class of agents That inhibit fungal protein synthesis. This review Describes the targets and mechanisms of action of all Classes of antifungal agents in clinical use or with Clinical potential.

Skin Physiology

The skin is the body's greatest organ, making up 15% of the adult body weight. It has an average surface area of 1.7 m², making it the largest organ in the body. The main job is to shield the inside organs from harmful radiation, temperature changes, and other environmental factors. The water content and heat loss from the body are also controlled by the skin. The epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis are the three layers that make up the skin. The dermis, or middle layer, and the epidermis, or outermost layer, are the layers that make up the dermis.

Skin Physiology

Epidermis

Epithelial cells, which can be alive or dead, make up the epidermis. A dense vascular network in the epidermis transports nutrients to the dermis underneath. Desmosomes link the cells of the epidermis. The intracellular keratin filaments are in touch with these desmosomes. Keratin is produced by these keratin filaments. During their maturity, keratin cells gather and form crosslinks with other keratin cells in the cytosol.

The epidermis contains a variety of cell types, including the following:

Keratinocytes: In the epidermis, keratinocytes make up 95% of all cells.

Melanocytes: These cells are present in the epidermis basal layer and are primarily responsible for producing the color melanin.

Langerhans cells: These crucial immunological cells can be found in the basal layer of the epidermis and the mid-dermis. Stratum germinativum (basal layer)

Stratum spinous

Epidermis consists of five layers namely

Stratum granulosum

Stratum lucidum

Stratum corneum

Stratum Germinativum

Since the cells in Stratum Germinativum have a significantly higher ratio of mitotic cells to total cells, this film is also known as the growing film. The layer of epidermal cells is continuously renewed by Stratum Germinativum. Basal cells have a nucleus and are columnar. The Stratum Germinativum keeps the skin's outer surface free of already-dead cells.

• Spinous Stratum

The structural and histochemical alteration of the cell's fundamental layer as it ascends and mounts produces the cells in the stratum spinous layer. The Stratum Spinous cells are joined together by large spikes or bristles that form desmosomes, which are bridge cells that bind cells together. The epidermis' integrity is maintained through a link between the cells.

Stratum Granulosum

The keratinocytes are covered by a cell layer called the stratum granulosum. The granular layer is another name for stratum granulosum. A zone of powerful biological chemical activity and structural alterations can be found in the stratum granulosum layer.

• Stratum Lucidum

The skin surface of the palm and sole both have a stratum lucidum layer. Over the granule film or sheet, stratum lucidum rapidly creates a thin, colourless, or glassy coating. Film cells from the stratum lucidum are not nucleated.

Stratum corneum

Stratum corneum refers to the epidermis's periphery-most outer layer. The skin's stratum corneum acts as a physical permeability barrier to stop excessive Trans epidermal water loss. The stratum corneum, the topmost layer of the epidermis, forms the primary skin barrier and

shields the body from the outside environment. The cells that make up the stratum corneum are flat, plate-like in shape, and 10–20 cell layers thick. SC cells have a width of 34–44 μm , a thickness of 0.5–0.20 μm , and a surface area of 750–1200 μm^2 . They are arranged similarly to cubicle-block-based walls. SC is made up of keratin (75–85%) and a variety of lipids (5–15%).

Stratum Granulosum

The keratinocytes are covered by a cell layer called the stratum granulosum. The granular layer is another name for stratum granulosum. A zone of powerful biological chemical activity and structural alterations can be found in the stratum granulosum layer.

- **Stratum Lucidum:** The skin surface of the palm and sole both have a stratum lucidum layer. Over the granule film or sheet, stratum lucidum rapidly creates a thin, colourless, or glassy coating. Film cells from the stratum lucidum are not nucleated.

- **Stratum corneum**

Stratum corneum refers to the epidermis's periphery-most outer layer. The skin's stratum corneum acts as a physical permeability barrier to stop excessive Trans epidermal water loss. The stratum corneum, the topmost layer of the epidermis, forms the primary skin barrier and shields the body from the outside environment. The cells that make up the stratum corneum are flat, plate-like in shape, and 10–20 cell layers thick. SC cells have a width of 34–44 μm , a thickness of 0.5–0.20 μm , and a surface area of 750–1200 μm^2 . They are arranged similarly to cubicle-block-based walls. SC is made up of keratin (75–85%) and a variety of lipids (5–15%), including phospholipids and cholesterol sulphate glycosphingolipids.

Types of antifungal

There are two types of antifungals: local and systemic. Local antifungals are usually administered topically or vaginally, depending on the condition being treated. Systemic antifungals are administered orally or intravenously. of the clinically employed azole antifungals, only a handful are used systemically. These include ketoconazole, itraconazole, fluconazole, fosfluconazole, voriconazole, posaconazole, and isavuconazole. Examples of non-azole systemic antifungals include griseofulvin and terbinafine.

Classification of Anti Fungal Drugs

Amphotericin B, ketoconazole and terbinafine are used systemically as well as topically.

POLYENE ANTIBIOTICS

- The name polyene is derived from their highly double-bonded structure.
- Amphotericin B is the prototype
- It is obtained from *Streptomyces nodosus*
- It is fungicidal at high and static at low concentrations.
- Cholesterol, present in host cell membranes, closely resembles ergosterol.
- The polyenes bind to it as well, though with lesser affinity.
- Thus AMB is one of the most toxic systemically used antibiotics
- Bacteria do not have sterols and are unaffected by polyenes.

Pharmacokinetics

1. AMB is not absorbed orally; it can be given orally for intestinal candidiasis without systemic toxicity.
2. Administered I.V. as a suspension made with the help of deoxycholate (DOC), it gets widely distributed in the body.
3. It can also be used intrathecally for fungal meningitis.
4. Topically for corneal ulcer (keratitis).

MOA

The polyenes have high affinity for ergosterol present in fungal cell membrane

They combine with it Get inserted into the membrane

Several polyene molecules together orient themselves in such a way as to form a ‘micropore’

Cell permeability is markedly increase

Ions, amino acids and other water-soluble substances move out

Cell death

Adverse effects

1. Infusion related acute reactions (most common)
2. Anemia.
3. Hypokalemia.
4. Phlebitis.
5. Headache, anorexia, vomiting, fever with chills (prevented by hydrocortisone)

USES

- It is the most effective drug for various types of systemic mycoses and is the gold standard of antifungal therapy.
- Cryptococcal Meningitis
- Systemic Aspergillosis
- Blastomycosis,
- Histoplasmosis,
- Mucormycosis
- Candidal Endocarditis

Formulation

Drug	Route of Administration	Oral Bioavailability	Elimination Half-Life	Routes of Elimination
Polyene Antibiotics				
Amphotericin B	Topical, IV, intrathecal, or intraventricular	NA	24 hours or 15 days†	Metabolism; renal excretion
Natamycin	Topical ocular	NA	NA	NA
Nystatin	Oral or topical	None	NA	NA
Azole Derivatives				
Clotrimazole	Topical	NA	NA	NA
Econazole	Topical	NA	NA	NA
Fluconazole	Oral or IV	95%	35 hours	Renal excretion
Itraconazole	Oral	55%	60 hours	Biliary, fecal, and renal excretion
Ketoconazole	Oral or topical	Highly variable	8 hours	Biliary and fecal excretion
Voriconazole	Oral or IV	96%	Dose dependent	Metabolism, renal excretion
Allylamine Drugs				
Naftifine	Topical	NA	2.5 days	Renal and fecal excretion
Terbinafine	Oral or topical	40%	12.5 days	Metabolism; renal excretion
Other Antifungal Drugs				
Caspofungin	IV	NA	11 hours	Metabolism
Ciclopirox	Topical	NA	NA	NA
Flucytosine	Oral	82%	3.5 hours	Renal excretion
Griseofulvin	Oral	Variable	16 hours	Metabolism; renal excretion
Tolnaftate	Topical	NA	NA	NA

OCULAR NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS OF ANTIFUNGAL ARGENT

Synthesizing novel active pharmaceutical ingredients with a desirable efficacy has always been a challenge for scientists. Unfortunately, many recently designed compounds have been

shown to be poorly soluble molecules with low permeability and high toxicity. As a result, scientists' attention has been drawn to the design of NDDS.

Generally, NDDS for ocular drug delivery are designed with two purposes:

- (1) make the drug controlled-release
- (2) increase its penetration to the cornea.

These efforts have resulted in NDDS, like liposomes, nanoparticles, microemulsions, nanoemulsions, self-emulsifying systems, niosomes, nanosuspension, dendrimers, nanomicelles, nanofibers, hydrogels, etc.

A Novel Transdermal Approach for Antifungal Drug Delivery

Fungi are eukaryotic organisms characterized by membrane-bound organelles and defined nuclei, distinguishing them from plants. Fungi were formerly included in the kingdom of plants, but because they have distinct physiological and structural characteristics and no chlorophyll, they should be placed in their own kingdom. The realm There are about 144,000 species of fungi that are known to exist, including moulds, yeasts, rusts, smuts, mildews, and mushrooms. Even though they resemble fungi, other creatures that resemble fungus, including slime moulds and oomycetes (water moulds), really belong to separate taxonomic groupings.

1 Fungal infections present with diverse signs and symptoms reliant on type and location of infection. For example, dermatophyte infections like *Tinea pedis* (athlete's foot) exhibit symptoms such as peeling, cracking, and scaling of feet, along with redness, blistering, or softening of skin, and burning or sweltering sensations.

2 Fungal infections are categorized based on virulence into primary and opportunistic pathogens. Primary pathogens cause infections in healthy individuals, typically originating in lungs and potentially spreading to other organ systems. These fungi are inherently virulent and often exhibit dimorphic characteristics, capable of transitioning between yeast and mold forms. Opportunistic pathogens, on the other hand, infect individuals with compromised immune defences, such as those with AIDS, undergoing immunosuppressive therapy, or experiencing alterations in normal flora due to antibiotics.

Examples of opportunistic fungal infections include Candidiasis, Cryptococcosis, and Aspergillosis.

ADVANTAGES OF TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

1. Reduction of doses as compared to oral dosage forms.
2. Ability to terminate the medications when needed.
3. The obviate of gastrointestinal repugnant.
4. Makes practical and effective use of Drugs molecule with less half-life.
5. The drug molecule with a narrow therapeutic window brings into service.
6. Improves patient compliance. Provide suitability of self-medication
7. Avoidance of first-pass metabolism.
8. Convenience and easy to apply.

Disadvantages of Topical Drug Delivery System

1. Dermatitis may occur on the skin due to skin irritation either because of drugs or excipients.
2. Drug molecules the poor skin permeability cannot be given through a topical drug delivery system.
3. Allergic reactions may develop at the application site
4. Drug molecule with larger particle size is difficult to absorb through the skin

DIAGNOSIS OF ANTIFUNGAL

1. Initial Assessment

Physical Exam: A doctor will look for visual signs of infection, such as rashes, scaling skin, hair loss, or discolored nails.

Symptom History: The provider will ask about your symptoms, their duration, and any other relevant health conditions, like immunosuppression

2. Sample Collection

Skin/Nail Infections: A scraping of skin, hair, or a nail clipping is taken.

Deeper Infections: For infections elsewhere in the body, samples of bodily fluids (e.g., blood, sputum, vaginal secretions, urine) or a tissue biopsy may be collected.

3. Laboratory Analysis

Microscopy: A sample is examined under a microscope to look for fungal elements, sometimes using special stains.

Fungal Culture: The sample is placed in a growth medium to identify the specific fungus by observing its growth pattern. This is considered a "gold standard" for definitive diagnosis but can take time.

Histopathology: A biopsy of deep tissue is examined to identify fungal elements and inflammatory responses within the tissue.

4. Advanced Diagnostic Tests

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR): Detects fungal DNA in a sample, providing faster results and high sensitivity.

Antigen/Antibody Tests: Detect specific fungal antigens in the blood or other body fluids to help diagnose infections.

Imaging Tests: For suspected deep-seated or invasive fungal infections, imaging like an X-ray might be used to look for fungal masses or other signs in organs like the lungs.

Treatment of antifungal agents

1. Topical Treatments

For skin infections: Creams, gels, sprays, or powders are used for mild infections like athlete's foot (*tinea pedis*), ringworm (*tinea corporis*), or fungal nail infections.

Examples: Clotrimazole, miconazole, ketoconazole, and terbinafine are common topical agents.

For moist areas: Powders can help keep areas like the groin or armpits dry, which is beneficial in treating fungal infections there.

2. Oral Treatments

For scalp ringworm and other widespread infections: Oral medications are prescribed.

Examples: Fluconazole, terbinafine, and griseofulvin are examples of oral antifungals.

3. Intravenous (IV) Treatments

For severe, invasive, or resistant infections: Intravenous (IV) administration is used for systemic fungal infections, such as those caused by resistant *Candida* species.

CONCLUSION

Now a days, antifungal drug resistance is becoming a most common problem in patients and is unavoidable due to wide availability and use of these agents.

There is considerable knowledge concerning the biochemical, genetic and clinical aspects of antifungal agent resistance. New agents and classes are a welcome addition to the antifungal armamentarium and results of ongoing clinical trials are eagerly awaited.

Newer broad-spectrum triazoles, in particular voriconazole and Posaconazole, display significant variability in bloodstream concentrations from one patient to the next that may necessitate TDM (Therapeutic Drug Monitoring) in select situations to guide drug therapy and dosing.

Long- term toxicities have become more of a concern because ambulatory patients with long-term immunosuppression are taking antifungal therapies for prolonged periods. However, the currently available antifungals have many limitations, including poor oral bioavailability, narrow therapeutic indices, and emerging drug resistance resulting from their use, thus making

It essential to investigate the development of novel drugs which can overcome these limitations and add to the antifungal armamentarium.

REFERENCE

1. Develoux, M. (2001) Griseofulvin. *Ann. Dermatol. Venere* 128: 1317–1325.
2. Woyke, T. Et al. (2002) Effect of auristatin PHE on microtubule Integrity and nuclear localization in *Cryptococcus neoformans*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 46: 3802–3808.
3. Pfaller, M.A. et al. (2002) In vitro activities of 5-fluorocytosine against 8,803 clinical isolates of *Candida* spp.: global assessment of primary Resistance using national committee for clinical laboratory standards Susceptibility testing methods. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 46: 3518–3521.

4. Brajtburg, J.K. et al. (1974) The molecular basis for the selective Toxicity of amphotericin B for yeast and filipin for animal oils. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 5: 377–382.
5. Dupont, B. (2002) Overview of the lipid formulations of amphotericin B. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 49: 31–36.
6. Zarif, L. Et al. (2000) Cochleates: new lipid-based drug delivery system. *J. Liposome Res.*, 10: 523–538.
7. Falk, R. Et al. (1999) A novel injectable water-soluble amphotericin B-arabinogalactan conjugate. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 43: 1975–1981.
8. Anonymous (2001) Liposomal nystatin – Nyotranw Antifungal. *Drugs Future* 26: 810.
9. Vanden Bossche, H. Et al. (1995) P450 inhibitors of use in medical Treatment: focus on mechanisms of action. *Pharmacol. Ther.*, 67: 79–100.
10. Kauffman CA. New antifungal agents. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med.*, 2004; 25: 233-239.
11. Sheehan DJ, Hitchcock CA, Sibley CM. Current and emerging azole Antifungal agents. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.*, 1999; 12: 40-79.
12. Walsh TJ, Groll A, Hiemenz J, et al. Infections due to emerging and Uncommon medically important fungal pathogens. *Clin. Microbiol. Infect.*, 2004; 10(1): 48-66.
13. Pfaller MA, Diekma DJ. Rare and emerging opportunistic fungal patho-Gens: concern for resistance beyond *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus Fumigatus*. *J Clin. Microbiol.*, 2004; 42: 4419-4431.
14. Martinez-Rossi NM, Peres ATN, Rossi A. Antifungal resistance mechanisms in dermatophytes. *Mycopathologia*, 2008; 166: 369-83.
15. Sanglard D, Bille J. Current understanding of the modes of action of and resistance mechanisms to conventional and emerging antifungal agents for treatment of *Candida* infections. In: Calderone R, Ed. *Candida and candidiasis*. USA: ASM Press, 2002; 349-83.
16. Parks LW, Casey WM. Fungal sterols. in *Lipids of pathogenic fungi*. eds Prasad R, Ghannoum. M. CRC Press, Inc. Boca Raton, Fla., 1996; 63–82.
17. Nozawa Y, Morita T. Molecular mechanisms of antifungal agents associated with membrane ergosterol. Dysfunction of membrane ergosterol and inhibition of ergosterol biosynthesis. in *In vitro and in vivo evaluation of antifungal agents*. eds Iwata K., Vanden Bossche H. Elsevier Science Publishers, B.V. Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 1986; 111.
18. Smith KJ, Warnock DW, Kennedy CTC, Johnson EM, opwood V, Van Cutesy J, et al. Azole resistance in *Candida albicans*. *J Med Vet Mycology*, 1986; 24: 133–144.

19. Orozco A, Higginbotham L, Hitchcock C, Parkinson T, Falconer D, Ibrahim A, et al. Mechanism of fluconazole resistance in *Candida krusei*. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 1998; 42: 2645–9.
20. Vanden Bossche H, Willemsens G, Cools W, Marichal HP, Lauwers WFJ. Hypothesis on the molecular basis of the antifungal activity of N- substituted imidazoles and triazoles. *Biochem. Soc. Tran.*